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Research Paper

Study On Avifaunal Diversity of Village Saroj Barewar, Jaunpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

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ABSTRACT

Avifauna plays a crucial role as a biotic component of an ecosystem, and it also serves as an indicator of the overall health of the ecosystem. The current study on avifaunal diversity was conducted from May 5, 2024, to June 5, 2024, in the village of Saroj Barewar, located in Jaunpur, Uttar Pradesh, India. During this period, a total of 41 bird species were recorded across 14 different orders and 25 families. The data was primarily collected through photographs and voice recordings from the study area. This research focuses on the avifaunal diversity of Saroj Barewar during the summer season. Further detailed studies related to Avifaunal diversity will be Carried out in future.

INTRODUCTION

Avifaunal diversity plays an important role in maintaining ecological balance. Birds are ecological indicators of environmental quality, and models for studying various of environmental problems they are very sensitive to the environmental changes [1]. Around 11,188 species of birds that grouped into 36 orders and 247 families have been globally identified [2]. India hosts around 1391 species making up

approximately 12% of world's avian population [3]. The country's biogeographic location, diverse physical features, and ecoclimatic variations contributes to its rich biodiversity [4]. The state of Uttar Pradesh with its variety of habitats—including forests, wetlands, grasslands, and urban areas—supports approximately 837 bird species [5]. Jaunpur district is ecologically significant as it is situated in Eastern Plain Zone of Gangetic Plain and its proximity to Gomti River. The surroundings of Gomti River have rich biodiversity, which includes diverse terrestrial

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flora and fauna as well as aquatic species of fishes, algae, gastropods, etc [6].The main objective of this research is to document the avifaunal diversity of Saroj Barewar, Jaunpur during the summer season. The study focuses on the identification of different species of birds and analysing ecological status. And also aims to provide data for future ornithological studies and conversation efforts, as the avifaunal diversity of this region is understudied despite its ecological significance.

MATERIAL/METHOD

Study Area:

Saroj Barewar village with latitude and longitude 25°37'18.7"N 82°56'29.3"E is located in the Kerakat tehsil of the Jaunpur district in the state of Uttar Pradesh, India. The total geographical area of the village is 169.19 hectares.

Data Collection:

The study was carried out from 5 May 2024 to 5 June 2024. Birds were observed randomly every day from morning to evening. Records are mainly based on photographs and Voice notes record. During the study, precautions were taken to avoid disturbance or any harm to the organisms.

Figure: 1 Shows the Satellite Image of Village - Saroj Barewar, Jaunpur, Uttarpradesh, India.

OBSERVATION TABLE

Table no.1 List of Avifauna Recorded From Village Saroj Barewar Near Gomti River

Sr.no	Order	Family	Common name	Scientific name	Food preferences	IUCN Status
1	Passeriformes	Corvidae	Large-billed Crow	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	O	LC
2		Passeridae	House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	G	LC
3		Sturnidae	Pied Myna	<i>Gracupica contra</i>	O	LC

4		Pycnonotidae	Red-Vented Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	F	LC
5		Leiothrichidae	Jungle Babbler	<i>Argya striata</i>	I	LC
6		Sturnidae	Bank Myna	<i>Acridotheres ginginianus</i>	O	LC
7		Motacillidae	White-browed Wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	I	LC
8		Sturnidae	Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	O	LC
9		Pycnonotidae	Red-whiskered bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	F	LC
10		Corvidae	Rufos Treepie	<i>Dendrocita vagabunda</i>	O	LC
11		Muscicapidae	Oriental Magpie Robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	I	LC
12		Muscicapidae	Brown Rock Chat	<i>Oenanthe fusca</i>	I	LC
13		Oriolidae	Black-hooded Oriole	<i>Oriolus xanthornus</i>	F	LC
14		Cisticolidae	Ashy Prinia	<i>Prinia socialis</i>	I	LC
15		Ploceidae	Baya Weaver	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	G	LC
16		Ploceidae	Streaked Weaver	<i>Ploceus manyar</i>	G	LC
17	Pelecaniformes	Threskiornithidae	Red-naped ibis	<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	I	LC
18		Ardeidae	Little Egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	C	LC
19		Ardeidae	Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	O	LC
20		Ardeidae	Indian Pond Heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	C	LC
21		Ardeidae	Striated Heron	<i>Butorides striata</i>	C	LC
22	Columbiformes	Columbidae	Rock Dove	<i>Columba livia</i>	G	LC
23		Columbidae	Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	G	LC
24		Columbidae	Spotted Dove	<i>Spilopelia chinensis</i>	G	LC
25		Columbidae	Laughing Dove	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i>	G	LC
26	Coraciiformes	Meropidae	Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	I	LC
27		Alcedinidae	White-throated Kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	C	LC
28		Alcedinidae	Pied Kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	C	LC
29	Cuculiformes	Cuculidae	Asian koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i>	F	LC
30		Cuculidae	Greater Coucal	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	O	LC
31	Galliformes	Phasianidae	Indian Peafowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	O	LC
32		Phasianidae	Grey Francolin	<i>Ortygornis pondicerianus</i>	G	LC
33	Piciformes	Megalaimidae	Coppersmith Barbet	<i>Psilopogon haemacephalus</i>	F	LC

34		Megalaimidae	Brown-headed Barbet	<i>Psilopogon zeylanicus</i>	F	LC
35	Charadriiformes	Charadriidae	Red-Wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	I	LC
36	Gruiformes	Rallidae	White-breasted Waterhen	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	O	LC
37	Suliformes	Phalacrocoracidae	Little Cormorant	<i>Microcarbo niger</i>	C	LC
38	Psittaciformes	Psittaculidae	Rose-ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	F	LC
39	Strigiformes	Strigidae	Spotted Owlet	<i>Athene brama</i>	C	LC
40	Bucerotiformes	Bucerotidae	Indian Grey Hornbill	<i>Ocyceros birostris</i>	F	LC
41	Ciconiiformes	Ciconiidae	White Stork	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	C	LC

[I: Insectivorous, F: Frugivorous, G: Granivorous, O: Omnivorous, C: Carnivorous, LC: Least Concern]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

During the study period, a total of 41 bird species belonging to 14 orders and 25 families were recorded (Table no.1). Out of the observed 14 orders, the avian species richness was highest for the order Passeriformes (16 species) followed by Pelecaniformes (5 species) ,Columbiformes (4 species), Coraciliformes (3 species), and Cuculiformes, Galliformes, Piciformes (2 species each) whereas orders with least number of species

were Charadriiformes , Gruiformes, Suliformes, Psittaciformes, Strigiformes, Bucerotiformes , Ciconiiformes (1 species each) (Figure.2). Among these species, the omnivorous diet group is dominant followed by carnivorous, insectivorous, granivorous and frugivorous .This variety in dietary composition showcases availability of diverse food resources. As per IUCN conservation all observed species are listed under Least Concern (LC). As per the prior research which was conducted during monsoon season, 51 species of bird were recorded [7]. This shows that monsoon provides optimal environmental conditions such as abundance of food, water and favorable climate.

Figure.2 : Showing Order wise Number and Percentage of Avifaunal Species recorded from Village Saroj Barewar

CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to study the avifauna of the Saroj Barewar village during summer season. A total number of 41 species were observed (Table no.1). This study reveals that Gomti River supports rich avifaunal diversity. This diversity is largely because of presence of agricultural fields, trees and water resources. However, compared to monsoon season , a decline in number of species observed during summer due to high temperatures and reduced water availability. The avifaunal diversity is also threatened by several anthropogenic activities. The overuse of chemical insecticides/pesticides in agriculture reduces insect population leading to decline in insectivorous birds, as they are their primary food source . Furthermore, various religious rituals and improper industrial waste disposal also pollute the Gomti River which serves as primary source of water for birds. There is need for conservation to mitigate these threats to ensure sustainability of

avifaunal diversity and overall ecosystem in this region.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no Competing interests exist.

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